

Appendix 4. “GRADE”* and “colloquial” language for communicating overall uncertainty

	“GRADE”	Colloquial We are....
Size of effect	High certainty evidence	
Important effect - i.e., lower CL > threshold for smallest important difference (“minimal clinically important difference”)	[Intervention] improves/reduces [outcome]	Very confident that X reduces Y a lot
Less important – i.e., upper CL < threshold for smallest important difference and lower CL > no difference	[Intervention] slightly improves/reduces [outcome]	Very confident that X reduces Y slightly/a little
No important benefit – i.e., point estimate close to no difference with narrow CI	[Intervention] makes little or no difference to [outcome]	Very confident that X does not reduce Y
	Moderate certainty evidence	
Important effect - i.e., lower CL > threshold for smallest important difference (“minimal clinically important difference”)	[Intervention] probably improves/reduces [outcome]	Somewhat confident that X reduces Y
Less important – i.e., upper CL < threshold for smallest important difference and lower CL > no difference	[Intervention] probably slightly improves/reduces [outcome]	Somewhat confident that X reduces Y slightly/a little
No important benefit – i.e., point estimate close to no difference with narrow CI	[Intervention] probably makes little or no difference to [outcome]	Somewhat confident that X does not reduce Y
	Low certainty evidence	
Important effect - i.e., lower CL > threshold for smallest important difference (“minimal clinically important difference”)	[Intervention] may improve/reduce [outcome]	X may reduce Y – but we are not very confident about this/about the evidence
Less important – i.e., upper CL < threshold for smallest important difference and lower CL > no difference	[Intervention] may slightly improve/reduce [outcome]	X may reduce Y slightly – but we are not very confident about this/about the evidence
No important benefit – i.e., point estimate close to no difference with narrow CI	[Intervention] may make little or no difference to [outcome]	X may not reduce Y – but we are not very confident about this/about the evidence
	Very low certainty evidence	
Any effect	We don’t know if/It is uncertain whether [intervention] improves/reduces [outcome] because the certainty of this evidence is very low.	We do not know if X reduces/affects Y

* Based on the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care Group’s guidance for communicating the certainty of evidence based on the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach to assessing the certainty of evidenceⁱ

ⁱ Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). Reporting the effects of an intervention in EPOC reviews. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2018.

<https://epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors>